

Impact of Visual Merchandising on Consumer Buying Behavior

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of visual merchandising on consumer purchasing decisions. It examines four key factors—product display, packaging, signage and labeling, and store layout design—to assess their impact on attracting customers and driving sales. Visual merchandising plays a critical role in shaping consumer perception and enhancing the shopping experience. Businesses often use these elements to create a visually appealing environment that encourages customers to explore products and make unplanned purchases. The research employed a descriptive quantitative approach, utilizing surveys distributed to 150 students from the College of Business and Administration at the Philippine Christian University. The Stratified Sampling Technique was used to ensure diverse representation among respondents, providing reliable data on how visual merchandising affects

consumer behavior in different demographics. Findings revealed that all four primary elements of visual merchandising—thoughtful store layouts, attractive packaging, eye-catching signage, and well-organized product displays—were highly effective in influencing consumer buying behavior. Notably, demographic factors such as gender showed no significant relationship with the effectiveness of visual merchandising strategies, suggesting that these techniques are universally effective across consumer groups. The study recommends that retailers and future business owners strategically utilize these merchandising techniques to enhance customer engagement and sales performance. Future research should explore the integration of technology-driven visual merchandising, such as digital displays and interactive elements, to maximize retail success.

Keywords: *Visual Merchandising, Retail Management, Consumer Behavior, Shopping Experience*

INTRODUCTION

The retail industry is constantly changing due to the dynamic nature of customer preferences, tastes, and purchasing behaviors (Tahiry et al., 2025). Visual merchandising is the strategic silent salesperson by presenting, attracting, inviting, informing, and convincing customers about the products towards the call to action (Cant & Wiid, 2020). Visual merchandising is evolving and expanding its horizon for retailers and customer experience (Singh & Shukla, 2022). According to Basu et al. (2022), visual merchandising is gaining significance in the field of modern retail research and application. Visual merchandising is essential for success in retail, both in physical and virtual environments, as it creates an engaging and strategic shopping experience that attracts, engages, and influences the consumer (Yde, 2024). Visual merchandising is of utmost importance in increasing foot traffic and retail sales, emphasizing the contributions of window display artists and interior display techniques, which convert prospects into customers. Effective shop design has become essential in attracting customers and boosting sales, as retail success depends heavily on visual merchandising (Anderson, 2025). Displaying products in ways that are appealing, accessible, and attractive, retailers can increase sales and improve their profit margins.

Stores make the most of their physical space and ensure that their marketing efforts and store display align with actual customer behavior by keeping the shopping experience fresh and engaging (Soni, 2021). Additionally, a store's ambiance plays a crucial role, with carefully coordinated colors enhancing the visual appeal of products. Creativity and inspiration are essential in designing compelling displays that attract customers and improve overall store aesthetics, ultimately contributing to increased sales and positive shopping experience.

Visual merchandising is both an art and a science and forms a significant part of retailing (Basha & Shyam, 2021). Visual merchandising has gained importance in contemporary retail research and practice (Basu et al., 2022). Visual merchandising is a strategic technique aimed at enhancing and showcasing a brand's appeal and unique features (Ceylan & Alomari, 2024). Also, it plays a key role in shaping the customer shopping experience (Prakash et al., 2024). Visual merchandising plays a pivotal role in creating a look, feel, and culture for the brand (Murali et al., 2024). Visual merchandising plays a role in both planned and non-planned purchases (Prakash et al., 2024). Visual merchandising aims to convey how to use or consume a product or service to customers while allowing retailers to integrate various elements to attract customer interest (Bailey & Baker, 2021). Visual merchandising is the brand and store's presentation due to teamwork of staff working in the store (Cuong, 2019). Creatively designed storefront displays can increase foot traffic and consumer engagement, leading to higher sales. This highlights how first impressions in retail can shape purchasing decisions (Opris & Bratucu, 2013). There are four dimensions of Visual merchandising: window display, in-store form/ mannequin in display, floor merchandising, and promotional signage (Mehta & Chugan, 2013a). However, retailers inconsistently observed Visual merchandising practices (Saranza et al., 2024).

Sight is one of the most used and crucial of the human senses in marketing. Colors, product and packaging design, logos, and images are all visual elements that are pivotal and can influence consumer perceptions (Bortolotti et al., 2023). Product display and visibility are crucial aspects in the arrangement of goods offered to consumers, with an attractive and unique arrangement to attract and captivate consumer purchase intentions (Afif et al., 2024). In retail, good product displays allow shoppers to quickly find what they're looking for, easily discover new features, and enjoy their shopping experience through their functional and aesthetic roles. (Feilong Acrylic, 2025). Product Display as an art form introduces, expresses, and transforms the store into an extraordinary, unique promotional platform (Raza et al., 2020).

The quality of a product is first seen in the quality of its package. Packaging is unofficially considered the fifth P of marketing as it plays a very important role in the company's offering and corporate image (Abude & Nwanko, 2023). The shape of the packaging gives an idea of the size of the product being packaged (Suma et al., 2023). Ton et al. (2024) theorizes that simple packaging makes the consumer more willing to pay. Packaging serves as both a protective and a marketing tool for building brand equity and boosting sales to increase consumer affluence, brand recognition, and unique design. Well-designed product packaging is considered one of the most important communication tools between the brand and the customer (Pawiński, 2021, in Ogonowski & Piwowarski, 2024).

In the context of retail design, the primary goal of signage is to facilitate the customer's shopping experience, efficiently guiding them through the commercial space (CAAD Retail Design, 2024). Beyond simply establishing a locational cue for consumers, signages offer a means by which to differentiate a retailer's brand from others (Auffrey, 2024). Influencing customer behavior during the moment of purchase, signage primarily aims to raise visibility and awareness and increase sales (Gooneratne et al., 2021). Signage is an effective means of communication between the retailer and the customer; it gives the store its unique identity and helps further its brand image. Readable fonts, strategic positioning, and color schemes can influence buying patterns by making shopping experiences more convenient and enjoyable (Cant et al., 2013).

Store layout is a key factor driving consumers' evaluation and response in the retail store and serves as an important factor in developing operations (Aseminachin, 2022; Tlapana, 2021). A store layout should provide a plausible shopping experience through excellent store atmosphere and in-store traffic patterns to enhance store loyalty and sales (Gul et al., 2022). According to Vinish et al. (2020), store layout is essential for fostering a pleasant retail environment and influencing customer behavior. Store layout is also considered a major predictor in the construction of the retail image (Vrechopoulos et al., 2004). A well-designed store layout encourages and exposes them to more merchandise, which is positively correlated with sales (Nguyen et al., 2022). Customers get a favorable impression of their shopping experience when the store layout is well-designed, and products are easily located (Tahiry et al., 2025).

Consumer behavior is a multidisciplinary field that incorporates insights from economics, psychology, sociology, and anthropology towards consumption decisions, reflecting both micro and macro-economic trends in marketing (Uwase, 2025). Consumer behavior refers to how customers satisfy their needs and wants by choosing, purchasing, using, and disposing of goods, ideas, and services (American Marketing Association, 2023). Consumer behavior is the mode of buying or repurchasing guided by criteria such as choice, consumption, quality, taste, advertising, or price expectations (Nasse, 2025). Consumer behavior reflects how individuals, groups, or organizations select, purchase, use, and dispose of ideas, goods, and services to fulfill their needs and desires (Manuere et al., 2022). It examines consumers' actions in the marketplace and the underlying motivations that drive these behaviors. Consumer buying behavior is multi-faceted and is dynamic to product characteristics (Singh, 2025). The researchers define consumer buying behavior as the total of a consumer's attitudes, preferences, intentions, and decisions regarding consumer behavior in the marketplace when purchasing a product or service. According to Nyagba and Tsetim (2022), consumer buying behavior is significantly influenced by window displays, lighting and illumination, and signage.

Specifically, it dwelt on the following questions:

1. What is the Demographic Profile of the respondents in terms of
 - a. Sex?

- b. Age?
- c. Monthly allowance/income?
- 2. What are the significant differences in the effectiveness of Visual Merchandising on consumer buying behavior in terms of:
 - a. Product Display?
 - b. Packaging?
 - c. Signage/ Label?
 - d. Store/ Layout Design?
- 3. Is there any significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondent in the effectiveness of Visual Merchandising on consumers' buying behavior in terms of:
 - a. Sex?
 - b. Age?
 - c. Monthly allowance/Income?

The two (2) hypotheses are developed from the dimensions found in the literature review of visual merchandising. Their relation in terms of visual merchandising is impulse buying behavior:

H0: There are no significant differences in the effectiveness of Visual Merchandising on consumers' buying behavior in terms of:

- a) Product Display
- b) Package
- c) Signage/ Label
- d) Store Layout design

H1: There is no significant relationship between the respondent's demographic profile in the effectiveness of Visual Merchandising on consumers' buying behavior in terms of Gender.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In conducting this study, the quantitative descriptive method was used. Quantitative research design is most appropriate when dealing with the collection and analysis of numerical data (Bhandari, 2023). The primary goal of descriptive research is to provide a detailed and accurate portrayal of the subject under study. Descriptive research seeks to describe a specific phenomenon, facts, situations, or conditions to provide a thorough and precise picture of the traits and actions of a specific phenomenon or subject of study without any scientific manipulation (Siedlecki, 2020). This type of research is particularly useful in identifying patterns, trends, and relationships within the data. As such, descriptive research is suitable to evaluate the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

The researchers used Stratified Sampling Technique, a method where a population is divided into smaller groups (strata) based on shared characteristics, and samples are randomly taken from each group. This ensures fair representation of all subgroups, improves accuracy, and reduces bias, especially in diverse populations among College of Business and Administration students. According to the study of Singh-

Ackbarali and Maharaj (2014), 75 to 150 consumers are necessary when testing product acceptability or liking.

The researchers made a survey questionnaire designed by the researchers. It was used as a data gathering instrument that focuses on the topic “Impact of Visual Merchandising on Consumer Buying Behavior”. The questionnaire consists of two parts: Part I, Demographic Profile of the respondents; and Part II, the evaluation of level of effectiveness of Visual Merchandising on Consumer buying behavior.

The data obtained from evaluation of effectiveness using Likert Scale to get the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising will be employed. The researchers will use the following statistical treatment to evaluate the result: Weighted mean for level of effectiveness, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), for significant differences, and Chi Square for significant relationships.

RESULTS

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	72	48%
Male	78	52%
Total	150	100%

Table 1 shows that fifty-two percent (52%) of the respondents are male, with a total of seventy-eight (78), while forty-eight percent (48%) are female, with a total of seventy-two (72) respondents, for a total of 150 respondents.

Table 2: Verbal Interpretation and Range of the Five-point Likert-type scale.

Verbal Interpretation	Value	Range
Very Effective	5	4.21-5.00
Effective	4	3.41-4.20
Moderately Effective	3	2.61-3.40
Least Effective	2	1.81-2.60
Not Effective at All	1	1.00-1.81

Table 2 shows that Product Display is an Effective factor of Visual Merchandising.

Product Display	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Orderly/Organized Design	84	51	14	0	1	150	4.45	VE
Colorful Display	63	45	41	1	0	150	4.10	E
Brand Segregation	62	55	30	3	0	150	4.17	E
External Display	60	53	30	5	2	150	4.09	E
Average Mean							4.21	VE

Table 3 shows that Product Display is a very effective factor of visual merchandising.

Table 4: Packaging as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Packaging	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
With Colorful Package	43	57	46	3	1	150	3.92	E
Safe and Reusable Pack	95	32	21	2	0	150	4.47	VE
Brand Recognition	61	63	22	4	0	150	4.21	VE
Convenient Packaging	88	44	16	2	0	150	4.45	VE
Average Mean							4.26	VE

Table 4 shows that Packaging is a very effective factor of visual merchandising.

Table 5: Signage and Labeling as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Signage and Labeling	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
With appropriate label	94	42	14	0	0	150	4.53	VE
Readable Signage	95	39	15	1	0	150	4.13	E
Unique Identity of the Store	64	63	18	5	0	150	4.24	VE
Easy access to the location	90	41	15	4	0	150	4.47	VE
Average Mean							4.34	VE

Table 5 shows that Signage/Labeling is a very effective factor of visual merchandising.

Table 6: Store Layout Design as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Store Layout Design	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Spacious	77	48	23	0	2	150	4.32	VE
Ventilation	83	49	14	4	0	150	4.41	VE
Ambiance	89	39	18	3	1	150	4.41	VE
Cleanliness	110	26	13	1	0	150	4.63	VE
Average Mean							4.44	VE

Table 6 shows that Store Layout Design is a very effective factor of visual merchandising.

Table 7: Overall Mean of the Factors of Visual Merchandising

Factor	W. Mean	V.I
Product Display	4.21	VE
Packaging	4.26	VE
Signage and Labeling	4.34	VE
Store Layout Design	4.44	VE
Overall Mean	4.31	VE

The table shows the summary of the effectiveness of each factor of Visual Merchandising. The overall mean rating is 4.44, with a verbal interpretation of Very Effective. Notably, among the weighted mean of each factor of Visual Merchandising, the Store Layout Design rated the highest among the different factors at 4.44, followed by Signage and Labeling at 4.34, Packaging at 4.26, and Product Display at 4.21, respectively.

Table 8: ANOVA Table.

Source	Sum of Square	Df	Variance	F Ratio
Between	0.20	3	0.02	1.75
Within	0.48	12	0.04	1.75
Total	8.68	15		

The computed F-ratio is 1.75, which is lower than the tabular value 3.49 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in the Impact of Visual Merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 9: Sex and Product Display as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Sex	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Female	135	101	47	4	1	288	4.28	VE
Male	134	103	68	5	2	312	4.16	E

Table 9 shows that sex and product display as a factor of visual merchandising for consumers' buying behavior is an effective factor in males and a very effective factor in females. The computed value using the chi-square is 3.25 lower than the tabular value, which is 3.25 at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is a significant relationship between gender and level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 10: Sex and Packaging as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Sex	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Female	140	103	42	3	0	288	4.18	E
Male	147	93	63	8	1	312	4.21	VE

Table 10 shows that packaging as a factor of visual merchandising for consumers' buying behavior is an effective factor in females and a very effective factor in males. The computed value using the chi-square is 7.20 lower than the tabular value, which is 9.49 at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, as there is a significant relationship between sex and the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 11: Sex and Signage/Labeling as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Sex	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Female	178	79	23	8	0	288	4.48	VE
Male	165	106	39	2	0	312	4.39	VE

Table 11 shows that signage/ labeling as a factor of visual merchandising for consumers' buying behavior is a very effective factor for both males and females. The computed value using the chi-square is 10.1407, which is higher than the tabular value, which is 9.49 at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, which means there is a significant relationship between sex and the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 12: Sex and Store Layout Design as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Sex	VE	E	ME	LE	NE	Total	W. Mean	V.I
Female	176	92	19	1	0	288	4.54	VE
Male	183	70	49	7	3	312	4.36	VE

Table 12 shows that Store Layout design as a factor of visual merchandising for consumers' buying behavior is a very effective factor for both males and females. The computed value using the chi-square is 22.95, which is higher than the tabular value, which is 9.49 at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected, which means there is no significant relationship between sex and the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

Table 13: Sex and Store Layout Design as an Effective Factor of Visual Merchandising on Consumers' Buying Behavior.

Sex	VE	VE	VE	VE
Female	178	79	23	8
Male	165	106	39	2

The computed value using the chi-square is 0.0026 lower than the tabular value, which is 2.35 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is no significant relationship between gender and the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising on consumers' buying behavior.

DISCUSSION

The study explored the impact of four primary elements of visual merchandising: product display, packaging, signage/labeling, and store layout design. Respondents indicate that the product display significantly influences consumer buying behavior, with respondents rating orderly and organized design (average weighted mean of 4.45) as highly effective. Branding segregation and colorful displays also had a substantial impact, encouraging impulse purchases and customer interest. Respondents identified safe and reusable packaging (average weighted mean of 4.47) as the most influential factor, followed closely by convenient and attractive packaging. Packaging that enhances brand recognition also plays a critical role in shaping purchase decisions. Regarding signage/labeling, the use of appropriate labels and readable signage was considered highly effective, with an average weighted mean of 4.53.

Signage promoting store identity and ease of location further enhances customer engagement. Regarding store layout design, respondents rated cleanliness and ambiance as very effective, with weighted means of 4.63 and 4.41, respectively.

The researchers conducted random sampling techniques on 150 respondents from the College of Business and Administration Students of Philippine Christian University. Semi-structured self-construct questionnaires using Likert Scale to get the level of effectiveness of visual merchandising will be employed. The research and data gathering will be conducted in the second semester of SY 2024-25. Sales and Promotions are not included in the research that influences consumer buying behavior.

5. Conclusion

Visual merchandising significantly impacts consumer behavior. Product displays, packaging, signage, and store layout are proven effective in driving customer engagement and influencing buying decisions. The study found no significant gender differences in the perceived effectiveness of visual merchandising. This indicated that businesses could implement uniform visual merchandising strategies for male and female customers.

Among the four elements, store layout and packaging emerged as the most influential factors in enhancing customer experience and purchase intentions. Retailers can boost sales and improve customer

satisfaction by optimizing store cleanliness, creating engaging displays, and using innovative packaging designs.

Prioritize store layout and cleanliness to create a welcoming and organized shopping environment. Invest in visually appealing and reusable packaging to enhance brand recognition and customer loyalty. Ensure that the signage is clear, readable, and strategically placed to guide customers effectively. For future retailers, consider the importance of visual merchandising elements, such as ambiance and organized product displays, in creating impactful retail strategies. Leverage customer feedback to improve visual merchandising practices.

For consumers, engage with retail environments by recognizing and valuing effective visual merchandising elements. Provide constructive feedback to store managers about aspects of visual merchandising that enhance or detract from the shopping experience. Lastly, future researchers must explore the integration of technology in visual merchandising, such as digital displays or augmented reality. Investigate the impact of cultural preferences on the effectiveness of visual merchandising strategies across diverse demographics.

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